

TEACHING GRAMMAR TO INTERMEDIATE LEVEL LEARNERS THROUGH CONTENT-BASED INSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT

Grammar has always held a central role in language teaching since it is the most fundamental aspects of language acquisition. Grammar rules are made easier if they are given in a context and teaching grammar in context articulates other skills too. This article explains why we should teach grammar in context and the use of grammar in content-based instruction and can be applicable in grammar-oriented language classes.

Teaching grammar has always held an important role in foreign language teaching. Through the history of language teaching, no other issue has been the topic of linguistic debate and throughout the period a number of claiming and counterclaiming suggestions have been made in favor of the importance of it or against it in language learning and teaching process. As a result of linguistic debates over grammar a number of linguistic theories, methodologies have come into existence and currently it is under issue of CEF (Common European of Reference for Languages). The way grammar has been or is should not be underestimated in terms of its influence on pedagogical grammar, learning process and many other stages included in foreign language acquisition. According to Newby [4, 236] “grammar is a subsystem in a network of other linguistic sub-systems and sub-skills.

Teaching content-based grammar slightly differs from traditional language classes

since content is focused on while teaching. In order to illustrate, teaching ends up as subordinate to the material that is being used in the English classrooms. According to the principles of the content, the instructor can all skills integrated while teaching grammar. Furthermore, teaching grammar continues as based on content through the whole course rather than a handful of lessons. For example, the teacher may start the course of teaching grammar on the topic of travelling using contents related to sub-themes to it. According to the specific techniques that the teacher frequently uses, a single content may be effectively used to teach a number of grammatical items. Based on the content that has been selected by a teacher beforehand, the instructor may make use of it for a previous grammar lesson together with a new one. Through this method, teachers may easily achieve grammatical accuracy.

Richard and Rogers [5, p78] suggest that “Content Based Grammar refers to an approach to second language teaching in which teaching is organized around the content or information that students will acquire rather than around linguistic or other types of syllabus. Content usually refers to the subject matter that people learn or transmit using language”. According to Brinton [1, p22] in content-based grammar students are exposed to interesting relevant content. He further said that this way of teaching allows the selection of content. Snow [8, p123] believed that “Content is the use of subject matter for second/foreign language teaching purposes. Subject matter may consist of topics or theme-based interest or need in adult EFL setting, or it may be very specific, such as the subjects that students are currently studying in their elementary classes.

With a reference to the role of grammar, Thornbury [10,p156] expresses that communicative competence means how successfully learners apply their grammar and vocabulary knowledge in order to achieve communicative goals, differentiating socially appropriate ways.

The role of instructional materials is crystal clear: to advertise communicative language use. In this point, Richards and Rodgers [5, p182] distinguishes three types of materials used: text-based materials, task-based materials and realia. Text-based materials are materials organized around a structural syllabus, but tasks involved are adapted towards communicativeness (Richards and Rodgers [5,82]). Task-based materials, in turn, may include role plays, games and communication-based exercises in which students have to demonstrate certain tasks. Realia are authentic, real life

materials. They incorporate language as in the way it is used in real life. Advertisements, newspaper articles, speeches of famous people, magazines and even interviews can be good examples of realia (Richards & Rodgers, [5, p82]). According to Richards and Rodgers, the differences between task-based and text-based tasks are quite vague as a single type of task can be regarded as both text-based and task-based material.

Throughout linguistic debates over the most appealing method to teach grammar, a number of questions have arisen; how should grammar be taught, why should grammar be taught or even should grammar be taught at all? When conducting grammar lessons, teacher find different methods applicable.

The most important part of understanding the content-based grammar is that specific concepts are associated with specific grammatical forms in our mind. For instance, students can differentiate present simple and future simple forms in terms of grammar and easily differentiate structures of forming them. However, both tense forms are translated into the Uzbek language with the same form (qiladi-present form, qiladi-future form). Although they have understood realm life situations in which either of the tenses is appropriate, they tend to use these two tenses interchangeably while communicating, for example, they will be impatient, yet intending to mean that they are impatient as these two forms are translated the same.

2.2 The proficiency level of intermediate level learners (who are intermediate level learners?)

Intermediate level learners in the English language can understand the main topics

that are being discussed including familiar topics such as leisure activities, work and school. Furthermore, in this level, learners can produce simple utterances on most situations related to familiar topics and those of personal interest. When it comes to their grammar knowledge, they have the ability of understanding tense forms with understanding of a number of phrasal verbs. And they are able to describe experiences and events together with hopes and dreams for the future. Their knowledge of a second language is equal to B1 level according to the marking criterion of CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) and a score between 4.0 and 5.0 in IELTS (International English Language Testing System).

2.3 Communicative Approaches that can be effective in teaching grammar to intermediate level learners.

As the principles of communicative based approaches allow active participation of students through exchange of context while teaching, they are rooted on main principles of communicative language teaching. Richard and Rogers claim that CBI is based on two main principles.

1) People can easily acquire the second language as they accept as a way of acquiring information rather than as an end in itself

2) Communicative based approaches better meets learners' needs to learn a second language. As it exposes learners to everyday life situation such as getting food, studying, getting a job and so on, learners' goal to learn combines with their daily needs resulting in better learning outcomes in the long run.

Brinton [1, p22-24], in turn, presented a few significant principles complementing

the ones suggested by Richard and Rogers [4, p78-79]. They are reflected in the following principles.

1. Base instructional decisions on content rather language criteria.

It is common to design books for second language learners mostly by course planners and material designers, not by language teachers. It is true that the responsibility of choosing material and adapting to be used in classroom language should be taken by language instructors especially CBI is being applied. Brinton [1, p22-24] points out that Communicative based approaches "allow the choice of content to dictate or influence the selection and sequencing of language items".

2. Integrate skills.

Communicative based approaches highlight integrated skills approach to language learning. For instance, any lesson may begin with a single aspect in priority including other linguistic features or multiple skills spontaneously as it happens in the real world.

3. Involve students actively in all phases of the learning process.

One of the main characteristics of CBI in the classroom is that the lesson is mainly student-oriented rather than relying on teacher's control all the time. In this type of classroom, students take initiative to organize and control learning process. Participating actively, students are welcome to accept peer evaluation and peer input compared to traditional classrooms.

4. Choose content for its relevance to students' lives, interests, or academic goals. Content should be relevant to students' needs and instructional settings. For example, inclusion of other subjects in

syllabus parallel to the content may be used, yet from different perspectives.

5. Select authentic texts and tasks.

Authenticity of materials is another distinguishing feature of communicative based approaches. It is true that usage of authentic materials identifies the pure purpose of communicative based approaches, but in turn, usage of them advertises learning the culture of the target language in order to allow students to understand the language subtleties of the target language such as prominence, linking, word stress, intonation and so on. Having understood, learners will find motivation and show a greater interest in learning the language. The chance to acquire linguistic abilities through the material that is interesting to them help them to expand their global knowledge of the target language.

To conclude, communicative based approach is an approach that activates communicative potential of a language and compatible with a wide range of classroom activities at the same time. According to Richards and Rodgers [5, p78-79] can be best defined by the principles below:

- *Learners acquire it by using it to communicate naturally;
- *Authentic and meaningful communication should be the target of classroom procedures;
- * Fluency should be a goal;
- *Communication entails integration among all skills and sub-skills;
- *Learning goes on a basis of creative construction and involves trial and error/elaboration.

Communicative Language Teaching has affected a number of other approaches and methodologies to language teaching.

Through the description and discussion of different views on Communicative Language teaching in great detail, the following criterion for the textbook analysis will be based on the following principles in this paper.

- Group or pair exercises (debates, discussions, role plays, tasks);
- Teaching grammar inductively;
- Language functions (grammar presented in the form of language functions)
- Contextualized forms of grammar linked to contextual features;
- Student-oriented exercises

The role of grammar within any communicative approach seems controversial partly because of aforementioned misconceptions or the so-called notion Natural Approaches which denies the importance of grammar in language learning.

However, it may be possible to solve this controversy if two main types of Communicative approach are discussed rather than talking about only one single type.

The shallow-end approach to Communicative Language Teaching explains that grammar rules should be learned beforehand in order to make learners apply them in communicational situations. Conversely, the deep-end approach to CLT holds the belief that grammar is acquired unconsciously during the performance of those communicative situations, therefore there is no use teaching grammar in advance.

According to these views, Communicative Language Teaching relies on grammar at least in its shallow-end approach. First, grammar rules are taught before appearing in those situations. According to Halliday [2, p16-18] both wordings and functions

are acquired through grammar with realization of functions and meanings. The fact that shallow-end approach deals with grammar does not mean that it is not communicative. But the fact that it is previously taught and then applied to communicative performance make that grammar truly meaningful and communicative. We can define this approach as inductive since students are not provided with grammar materials to learn, but they are provided with examples to infer on their own. According to Rutherford [6, p42] through this consciousness-raising the teacher makes learners relate what grammar rules they have learned before with new grammar item or even grammatical information in their L1.

Contrary to shallow-end approach, the deep-end methodology together with Krashen's theories [3, p 156] as he reflected his ideas on Natural Approach, neglects the role of grammar in communication claiming that it should be acquired unconsciously rather than being taught. There is still a belief that grammar may hinder communication as it is considered conscious reflection about grammar brings about negative effects for input processing and performance.

Even though contradictions about teaching grammar still exist, the deep-end approach is not currently used in classroom languages, as most authors and teachers recognize the role of grammar without discriminating the main target of communication.

The shallow end approach allows learners to acquire linguistic features first as it goes in deductive approach. The shallow-end approach to Communicative based methodology explains that grammar rules

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conscious reflection about grammar brings about negative effects for input processing and performance.

To conclude, shallow-end approach makes second language acquisition a conscious process, as a second language teacher I accept that a good operational command of the English language that I have now is mainly due to having acquired grammatical items first and then application of them into different life situations, the way that I create a piece of writing would not be that impressive through deep-end approach as no kind of a learner is not exposed to full

second language atmosphere as he/she had with his/her mother tongue.

As a language teacher, I can say from my experience that in CLT classrooms, learners unconsciously apply the forms that they have learnt. If a teacher presents a material using deep-end approach, it may take a long time to use them effectively into real life situations. Therefore, shallow-end approach should be used before making a freer production. If a learner understands the grammatical functions, communicative competence can easily be achieved as he/she can produce other forms related to the grammar topic learnt independently.

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